

Assessing the Adoption and Utilization of ICT-Based Innovations for Improved Library Services in Federal University Libraries in Northwest Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The rapid evolution of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has significantly transformed the provision of library services, necessitating academic libraries to adopt innovative tools for improved access, efficiency, and user satisfaction. This study assesses the adoption and utilization of ICT-based innovations for improved library services in federal university libraries in Northwest Nigeria. Five objectives and five research questions guided the study. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study population comprised library staff, heads of ICT units and library users drawn from federal university libraries in Northwest Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select six federal universities in the zone. Within each university, 10 librarians/library staff and 10 active library users, totaling 120 respondents were selected for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection in the study. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics using frequency, percentage tables and mean score. The study revealed that while technologies such as integrated library system, online public access catalogue, digital library/e-resources portal, and institutional repository have been adapted to varying degrees, their utilization remains hindered by inadequate funding, insufficient staff training, poor ICT infrastructure, and irregular maintenance. Nevertheless, positive attitudes towards technology adoption were observed among staff, highlighting potential for improvement with targeted intervention. The study recommends increase funding and investment; improve ICT infrastructures, capacity building and training, awareness and sensitization campaigns among others. These measures are crucial for federal university libraries in Northwest Nigeria to meet the evolving information needs of students, researchers, faculty in the digital age.

Keywords: Innovative Technologies, Library services, Adoption, Utilization, Federal University Libraries.

Introduction

Libraries are the intellectual backbone of universities, providing access to knowledge, supporting teaching, and enabling research. In the era of digital transformation, the role of university libraries is rapidly changing as they adopt ICT-based innovations to improve service delivery. These

innovations include integrated library management systems (e.g., KOHA), digital libraries, online public access catalogues (OPAC), Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), digital cataloguing systems, electronic databases, cloud storage, artificial intelligence tools, mobile applications, and institutional repositories. Their adoption has transformed how information is stored, accessed, and shared, making libraries more efficient and user-friendly (Ojobor, Okafor, & Ugwuanyi, 2025; Oketunji, 2020). Similarly, Adebayo & Aboyade (2021) noted that as universities move into the digital age and information needs grow more complex, using ICT-based innovations has become an essential way to improve library services so their adoption is essential for libraries to remain relevant in a rapidly evolving digital environment where users expect on demand, remote access to scholarly resources.

Federal universities in Nigeria, especially those located in Northwest zone, university libraries are increasingly recognizing the need to embrace such innovations. However, the level of adoption and actual utilization varies widely due to differences in institutional funding, ICT infrastructure, staff ICT literacy, and management commitment (Iwhiwhu, Ruteyan & Eghwubare, 2019). While some libraries have moved toward full automation and established digital repositories, others still struggle with challenges ranging from inconsistent internet connectivity and electricity supply, limited budget allocations and shortage of skilled personnel (Garba & Shehu, 2022). These factors potentially hinder the smooth integration and sustainable use of ICT-based innovations in library operations there by rely heavily on manual processes and limited access to online resources.

Globally, university libraries are moving towards digital transformation, integrating systems that allow seamless access to scholarly materials and interactive services. Nigerian libraries are striving to keep pace, but studies show that adoption levels remain low compared to international standards (Asifor & Ogbomo, 2025). Research have shown that successful adoption depends on factors such as perceived usefulness, ease of use, organizational support, and staff training. Without these, even when technologies are introduced, they may remain underutilized.

Assessing the situation in Northwest Nigeria is particularly important because federal universities in this region serve a large population of students and researchers. Understanding how these libraries adopt and utilize innovative technologies will reveal both the progress made and the gaps that remain. Such an assessment will also highlight strategies for overcoming barriers and maximizing the benefits of digital tools. In a similar vein, previous studies (e.g., Ogbomo & Ogbomo, 2020; Ani, 2017) have shown that while many university libraries are aware of the benefits of technological innovations, actual utilization is often low due to various institutional and contextual barriers. This calls for a region-specific assessment that will shed light on the extent to which libraries in federal universities of Northwest Nigeria are adopting and utilizing ICT-based innovations, the challenges they face, and the impacts these technologies have on service delivery.

Ultimately, effective adoption and utilization of ICT-based innovations will position federal university libraries in Northwest Nigeria as modern academic hubs capable of meeting global standards and supporting the knowledge economy. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the adoption and utilization of ICT-based innovations for improved library services in federal universities in Northwest Nigeria. The study aims to explore the types of technologies in use, the degree of their integration, user satisfaction, challenges encountered, and the strategies needed for

more effective implementation. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for library administrators, policymakers, and ICT planners in the higher education sector.

Statement of the Problem

University libraries serve as critical support systems for teaching, learning, and research. With the rapid evolution of digital technologies, the traditional roles of libraries are being redefined. In response, academic libraries globally are integrating innovative technologies to automate services, enhance user experiences, and provide seamless access to both physical and digital resources (Adebayo & Aboyade, 2021). These technologies, ranging from integrated library systems and digital repositories to RFID, OPAC, and mobile library applications offer opportunities for improved efficiency, resource accessibility, and user satisfaction (Oketunji, 2020).

In federal universities of Northwest Nigeria, the adoption of ICT-based innovations in library services has gained increasing attention. Despite the recognition of their potential, empirical evidence suggests that the actual level of adoption and effective utilization remains inconsistent and, in many cases, inadequate (Garba & Shehu, 2022). While some university libraries have embraced full automation and provided digital access to their collections, others still struggle with manual operations, poor ICT infrastructure, and low levels of staff digital literacy.

Several factors have been implicated in the slow pace of technology adoption in academic libraries in this region. These include limited funding, unreliable power supply, poor internet connectivity, lack of technical support, and resistance to change among library personnel (Iwhiwhu, Ruteyan & Eghwubare, 2019). Additionally, there is often a lack of institutional policy frameworks that prioritize technological innovation and staff capacity building in university libraries.

Furthermore, there is insufficient empirical data on the extent to which these technologies are being adopted and used in Northwest Nigeria's federal university libraries. Without such data, it is difficult to make informed decisions regarding investment, policy formulation, and strategic planning. More importantly, the impact of these technologies on the quality and efficiency of library services in the region remains under-researched. Given these concerns, it is imperative to assess the status of ICT-based innovations adoption and utilization in library services within federal universities of Northwest Nigeria. This will help identify existing gaps, understand contextual barriers, and provide actionable recommendations for improving library services through effective technological integration.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to assess the adoption and utilization of ICT-based innovations for enhancing library services in federal universities located in Northwest Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the types of ICT-based innovations adopted by federal university libraries in Northwest Nigeria.
2. Examine the extent to which these technologies are utilized in delivering library services.

3. Assess the perceived impact of the adopted technologies on the quality of library services.
4. Investigate the challenges hindering the effective adoption and utilization of ICT-based innovations in university libraries.
5. Determine the strategies put in place by university libraries to promote technology-driven service delivery.

Research Questions

To achieve the above objectives, the study will address the following research questions:

1. What types of ICT-based innovations have been adopted in the library services of federal universities in Northwest Nigeria?
2. To what extent are these technologies being utilized in the day-to-day operations of these libraries?
3. What are the perceived effects of these technologies on the quality and efficiency of library services?
4. What challenges do university libraries face in adopting and utilizing ICT-based innovations?
5. What strategies are being implemented to enhance the adoption and use of innovative technologies in federal university libraries?

Literature Review

Concept of Innovative Technologies in Library Services

ICT-based innovations in library services refer to the application of modern tools and digital systems that enhance how information is acquired, stored, organized, retrieved, and delivered to users. These include integrated library systems (e.g., KOHA), Online Public Access Catalogues (OPAC), digital libraries, institutional repositories, RFID, cloud computing, mobile library apps, and artificial intelligence (Oketunji, 2020; Aina, 2021). Raji (2018) refer innovative technologies as those technologies used to collect, store, edit and communicate information in various format. These technologies according to the author are used to improve access to digital information, narrow down the digital divide and improves standard of living. Adoption of ICT in libraries is a way of improving on information services provided in libraries (Adebayo, Ahmed & Adeniran, 2018). Innovative technologies also refer to all technologies used to handle telecommunications, broadcast media, intelligent building management systems, audiovisual processing, transmission systems, and network-based control and monitoring functions (Ogunu & West, 2024).

Tukur and Adamu, as cited in Adebayo, Ahmed, and Adeniran (2018), defined innovative technologies as computer-based tools and internet resources used to provide information and communication services to a broad audience. The term encompasses various technologies such as

telephones, email, and more, with the internet playing a key role in transmitting different types of data including text, images, audio, and video. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) serve as a system for gathering, analyzing, processing, and distributing information. These technologies are widely applied, particularly in transforming traditional paper-based records into digital formats for easier storage, retrieval, and dissemination. In modern libraries and information centers, innovative technologies are considered essential tools.

In academic libraries, these technologies support seamless access to information resources, improve operational efficiency, and expand the reach of library services to remote users (Ani, 2017). As higher education institutions increasingly move toward digital learning and research environments, academic libraries are compelled to innovate to remain relevant and responsive to the evolving needs of students and researchers (Gyamfi, 2020).

Academic libraries have been using innovative technologies to deliver services that meet the varying information needs of their users. These libraries are rapidly transitioning to technology-driven resources and services. Traditional materials are being quickly replaced by digital alternatives such as e-journals, CD-ROMs, online databases, e-books, web-based resources, and other electronic formats. The advancement of these technologies in libraries has significantly boosted the use of information resources for delivering services. This development has enabled libraries to extend their services beyond their physical locations. Consequently, library collections are no longer confined to traditional tools but now include various online resources made accessible through technology. The primary goal is to improve service delivery by offering timely and up-to-date resources outside the library's physical space. Without embracing these technologies, libraries would remain bound to outdated, time-consuming service methods, which contradict two fundamental principles of librarianship: "save the time of the user" and "the library is a growing organism."

Adoption and Utilization of **ICT-based innovations** in University Libraries

The adoption and utilization of innovative technologies in university libraries have transformed the way information resources and services are delivered. These technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, the Internet of Things (IoT), augmented and virtual reality, and integrated library systems, are redefining the roles and capabilities of academic libraries.

The increasing demand for digital information, changing user expectations, and the need for efficient information management are key drivers of technology adoption in academic libraries (Olanrewaju & Adebayo, 2021). Libraries must adapt to the dynamic information landscape characterized by the proliferation of digital content and online academic platforms. Oladokun and Aina (2022) also note that competitive academic environments and global educational trends are pushing university libraries to embrace innovation to remain relevant. In many university libraries, the adoption of innovative technologies has led to improved service delivery, but the level of utilization varies significantly. According to Oyediran and Ojo (2020), some libraries in Nigeria have integrated online public access catalogs (OPACs), electronic databases, and institutional repositories to support teaching and research. However, utilization is often limited by infrastructural challenges and inconsistent policy support.

In contrast, university libraries in technologically advanced regions are leveraging AI for information retrieval, digital assistants, and automated indexing. As reported by Cox et al. (2021), libraries in the UK and North America have begun integrating machine learning and data analytics to personalize user experiences and enhance decision-making.

In Nigeria, several university libraries have adopted systems like KOHA and have developed digital repositories and portals for accessing e-journals and e-books. However, the level of actual utilization varies due to institutional differences in leadership, staff ICT competence, and infrastructural development (Adebayo & Aboyade, 2021). Studies show that while many libraries have acquired software tools, their full potential is not always utilized due to poor implementation strategies and limited user training (Ekere, Ugwu & Eze, 2020). In supporting this point Ogunu & West (2024) stated that even though library and information centers have adopted innovative technologies to satisfy the information needs of their users, however, these technologies are not utilized fully. Non utilization of these technologies according to Umana (2018) is a cause of major concern to librarians worldwide.

Benefits of ICT-based innovations Integration in Library Services

In recent times, several new technologies have been introduced, and many of these innovations are now employed within libraries. Artificial Intelligence-powered robots have made their way into various sectors, including libraries, performing tasks beyond human capability with greater efficiency. These technologies have the potential to address and provide new opportunities for advancement in library services (Rathna & Divyananda, 2018). They offer answers to a range of problems, help with the growth of a range of existing facilities, and offer opportunities to build new ones.

Adopting ICT-based innovations offers several advantages. It improves access to information, enhances user satisfaction, and facilitates remote learning and research. Tella (2020) state that automation tools and digital platforms have made it easier for users to access resources at any time and from anywhere. Additionally, technologies like AI and data analytics help libraries to anticipate user needs, streamline workflows, and ensure efficient resource management (Lund & Wang, 2023). Vysakh (2020) and Frey (2014) assert that emerging technologies are being utilized in library service delivery. Neogi and Partap (2019) highlight the benefits of emerging technologies in library services when he mentioned that technologies boost libraries' capability to provide better and faster services. They also influence librarians' and libraries' creativity, problem-solving skills, and self-image. Furthermore, they support the processing of innovations and add value to existing products and services. These technologies strengthen library knowledge and expand opportunities for the future, make it simple to deliver quick services, and help save time.

Despite the multiple issues confronting academic libraries in Nigerian, there are opportunities to find and deploy new and emerging technologies to provide library services while remaining relevant to society.

Challenges in the Adoption and Utilization of Technologies in Nigerian University Libraries

Despite the recognized benefits, university libraries in Nigeria face numerous challenges in adopting and effectively using innovative technologies. This can be seen in various studies carried out by scholars in Nigeria. For example, Tella (2020) discusses the infrastructural deficiencies that hinder the deployment of robotics, noting that many libraries lack the physical and technical environment necessary to accommodate these systems. Furthermore, a study by Usman and Abdullahi (2021) in Northern Nigerian universities revealed that while many libraries had adopted integrated library systems, less than 40% of the libraries used them fully for all core operations. Another study by Garba and Shehu (2022) focused on federal universities in Northwest Nigeria and highlighted poor internet services, limited digital resources, and lack of staff motivation as key barriers to technology integration.

Financial challenges remain a significant obstacle for the adoption and use of emerging technologies in Nigeria's academic libraries. This has been confirmed by Oladokun et al. (2023) who maintained that the acquisition and upkeep of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and robotics often surpass the financial capabilities of academic libraries. This issue is worsened by insufficient government support and a lack of alternative funding sources for technological upgrades. In addition, the preparedness and skill level of library staff to embrace and use these technologies is also a major issue as Owolabi et al. (2022), Lund and Wang (2023) emphasize that many librarians lack access to the necessary training and professional development to build the expertise needed for integrating AI and robotics. The mismatch between technology deployment and staff skills weakens the overall effectiveness of implementation.

Cultural and ethical barriers also hinder the integration of new technologies. Yoon, Andrews, and Ward (2022) note that fears about job loss and concerns over user privacy often shape negative attitudes toward AI. Ajani et al. (2024) further explain that public skepticism about robotics and AI within libraries can lead to resistance from both staff and users, slowing down adoption. Additionally, the lack of comprehensive policies and strategic direction is another limitation. Cox (2023) stresses the importance of developing strong governance structures and ethical frameworks to navigate the complexities of AI-enabled services. In the absence of such measures, the use of emerging technologies in Nigerian academic libraries remains inconsistent and poorly coordinated.

Strategies for enhancing technology use in University Libraries

To enhance technology use in university libraries, strategies should focus on integrating digital resources, improving user training, and promoting user-friendly interfaces. This includes expanding access to online databases, offering mobile-friendly services, and providing robust digital literacy training programs. Ifijeh & Yusuf (2019) advocates for continuous training for librarians and users to enhance ICT skills. Ekere et al. (2020) calls for adequate funding and ICT infrastructure development as a strategy for enhancing ICT use in academic libraries. Others include; **policy formulation** that prioritizes library innovation in university planning, **monitoring and evaluation** of technology implementation progress, **collaboration** with tech vendors and donor agencies for support

Effective leadership, commitment from university management, and advocacy from library associations also play key roles in driving innovation (Oketunji, 2020). By implementing these

strategies, university libraries can effectively leverage technology to enhance the learning and research experience for their users, ensuring that the library remains a vital hub of information and innovation.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design is appropriate because it enables the researcher collect data from a large population to describe and analyze current practices, perceptions, and challenges related to the adoption and use of ICT-Based Innovations in library services. The study population comprised librarians, head of ICT units, and library users drawn from federal university libraries in Northwest Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select six federal universities in the zone. These are: Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Bayero University Kano, Usmanu Danfodio Sokoto, Federal University Dutse, Federal University, Birnin Kebbi, and Federal University Gusau. Within each university, 10 librarians/library staff and 10 active library users, totaling 120 respondents were selected for the study. The selection was done to ensure equitable representation across the participating institutions. Furthermore, the decision to select an equal number of respondents from each university was intended to facilitate meaningful comparisons among institutions and to prevent any single university from disproportionately influencing the findings.

Questionnaire was the instruments used for data collection. **The structured questionnaire was designed for librarians and the library users. The instrument was validated by experts in library and information science department, Bayero University, Kano. A pilot test was conducted in Yusuf Maitama Sule University, Kano (not included in the main sample) to check for clarity, consistency, and reliability.** The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The analysis yielded a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.84, indicating a high level of internal consistency among the questionnaire items. Since the obtained coefficient exceeded the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.70, the instrument was considered reliable for data collection. **Questionnaire was distributed electronically via Google form and emails. The quantitative data collected was analyzed descriptively using frequencies, percentages and mean score to summarize their responses.**

Results and Discussion

Response Rate

Table with 4 columns: Item, Distributed, Returned, Response Rate (%). Rows include Questionnaires (Staff), Questionnaires (Users), and Total.

Table above indicates that 120 copies of questionnaire were distributed to both staff and users (60 copies each). Out of this number, 107 copies were duly filled and returned for analysis which represent 89.2% return rate.

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table with 4 columns: Variable, Category, Frequency, Percentage (%). Rows include Gender (Male/Female), Age (18-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46+), and Status (Librarian/ICT staff, Library Users).

Findings above show that there are more male library users than their female counterpart. This is an indication that majority of the library users in any type of library were male.

Research Question 1: What types of innovative technologies have been adopted?

Here, respondents were asked to indicate the type of technologies adopted in their respective institutional libraries. Their responses are indicated below:

Table with 5 columns: Technology Type, Adopted (F, %), Not Adopted (F, %). Rows include Integrated Library System, OPAC, Digital Library, Institutional Repository, RFID & Smart Cards, and Mobile Library App.

Findings from table above reveals that most of the libraries investigated have adopted basic technologies like KOHA, OPAC, and digital resources. More advanced systems like RFID and mobile apps are less commonly implemented.

Research Question 2: To what extent are these technologies utilized?

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent of utilization of the available technologies in their respective libraries. Their responses are presented below. Note that any item with a mean score between **3.40 and 4.19** was interpreted as indicating **high utilization**, while mean scores between **2.60 and 3.39** were interpreted as indicating **moderate utilization**.

Statement	Mean Score	Interpretation
Technologies are regularly used in operations	3.9	High utilization
Users are trained to use technologies	3.3	Moderate
Staff are confident using library technologies	3.7	High
E-resources are frequently accessed by users	3.8	High
Self-service features (e.g., OPAC) are fully utilized	3.2	Moderate

The findings indicate that ICT-Based technologies are generally well utilized in library operations. High levels of utilization were reported for regular technology use in operations (Mean = 3.9), staff confidence in using library technologies (Mean = 3.7), and frequent access to e-resources by users (Mean = 3.8). However, user training on technologies (Mean = 3.3) and utilization of self-service features such as OPAC (Mean = 3.2) were only moderate, suggesting areas where further improvement and capacity building efforts may be required.

Research Question 3: What is the perceived impact on library services?

On perceived impact of emerging technologies on library services, respondents responded as follows;

Statement	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)
Technologies have improved access to information	92%	8%
Services are faster and more efficient	89%	11%
Users are more satisfied with digital access	81%	19%
Technology supports teaching and research activities	85%	15%

Respondents believe that the integration of emerging technologies has positively influenced service quality and user satisfaction.

Research Question 4: What challenges hinder adoption and utilization?

To identify challenges that hinder the adoption and utilization of emerging technologies for enhanced library services, respondents give their responses below;

Challenge	% of Respondents Affected
Poor internet and power supply	88%
Insufficient funding	76%
Lack of regular staff training	65%
Resistance to change from some staff	42%
Low user awareness of digital tools	58%

Infrastructure (88%) and funding (76%) are the major challenges affecting the adoption and utilization of emerging technologies in academic libraries under study as indicated in the table above. This is followed by inadequate staff training (65%) and low user awareness 58%.

Training and user awareness are very critical issues when talking about the adoption and utilization of emerging technology, so therefore needs urgent attention.

Research Question 5: What strategies are being implemented or recommended?

From the interviews conducted, the following strategies emerged. This was done in narrative format:

Respondents emphasized the need to establish technology upgrade plans and form digital library committees to guide the integration of new systems. They highlighted the importance of organizing regular workshops and ICT training for both staff and users to build capacity and keep pace with technological changes. Many participants stressed the value of seeking partnerships with donor agencies and ICT vendors to secure funding and technical support. Strengthening university-level ICT policies to explicitly incorporate library operations was also identified as a crucial step. In addition, respondents noted that improving bandwidth and providing reliable backup power solutions would significantly enhance the efficiency and reliability of library services.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study revealed that most of the libraries in Federal Universities in Northwest Nigeria have adopted core ICT-Based Technologies like KOHA and digital repositories. This is consistent with the findings of Adebayo & Aboyade (2021) who found that in Nigeria, several university libraries have adopted systems like KOHA and has developed digital repositories and portals for accessing e-journals and e-books. The deployment of these technologies in libraries can help address and provide new opportunities for advancement of library services. According to Rathna & Divyananda (2018), innovative technologies offer an answer to a range of problems, help with the growth of a range of existing facilities, and offer opportunities to build new ones.

Regarding extent of utilization of these technologies, findings revealed high utilization among library staff, and moderate among users. The application and use of innovative technologies in academic libraries have transformed the way information resources and services are delivered. These technologies are redefining the roles and capabilities of academic libraries. What triggered libraries to integrate innovative technologies into their services are the increasing demand for digital information, changing user expectation, and the need for efficient information management.

These according to Olanrewaju & Adebayo (2021) are key drivers of technology adoption in academic libraries. Efficient utilization of these technologies will bring about user satisfaction and effective service delivery. This finding therefore, is contrary to the findings of Oyediran and Ojo (2020), Adebayo & Aboyade (2021), Ekere, Ugwu & Eze (2020), Ogunu & West (2024) stated that even though library and information centers have adopted innovative technologies to satisfy the information needs of their users, however, these technologies are not utilized fully. Non utilization according to Umana (2018) is a cause of major concern to librarians worldwide.

This discrepancy may be attributed to changes that have occurred in the higher education and library sectors in recent years. Since the conduct of the earlier studies, many academic libraries have increased investments in information and communication technologies, digital resources, staff capacity development, and automated library services. The COVID-19 pandemic also accelerated the adoption of digital technologies in academic institutions, compelling libraries to expand electronic services and enhance staff competencies in the use of emerging technologies.

Findings further indicate that both staff and users believe that integrating ICT-based technologies has positively influenced service quality and user satisfaction. It improves access to information, enhances user satisfaction, and facilitates remote learning and research. This finding aligns with Tella (2020), who demonstrated that automation tools and digital platforms improve resource accessibility, supporting the positive impact observed in this study.

The study further identifies Infrastructure, funding, inadequate staff training, and low user awareness as the major challenges affecting the adoption and utilization of innovative technologies in academic libraries investigated. This is consistent with the findings of Oladokun et al. (2023) who found that the acquisition and upkeep of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and robotics often surpass the financial capabilities of academic libraries. This is not healthy for the development of academic libraries in Nigeria. In addition, the preparedness and skill level of library staff to embrace and use these technologies is also a major issue as Owolabi et al. (2022), Lund and Wang (2023) emphasized that many librarians lack access to the necessary training and professional development to build the expertise needed for integrating AI and robotics.

Lastly, the study highlighted measures being implemented to enhance the adoption and use of ICT-based technologies in academic libraries in Northwest Nigeria. The measures include establishing technology upgrade plans and digital library committees, conducting regular workshops and ICT training for staff and users, seeking partnerships with donor agencies and ICT vendors, strengthening university-level ICT policies that incorporate libraries, and improving bandwidth as well as backup power solutions.

Implementing these measures will significantly enhance the capacity of libraries to leverage modern technologies in service delivery. By establishing clear upgrade plans, investing in continuous training, fostering strategic partnerships, aligning with institutional ICT policies, and improving infrastructure such as bandwidth and backup power, libraries will be better positioned to meet the evolving needs of their users and remain relevant in the digital age.

Conclusion

The integration of innovative technologies in university libraries is pivotal to enhancing the quality, reach, and responsiveness of information services in the digital age. Findings from this study affirm that Federal University libraries in Northwest Nigeria are making significant strides toward adopting essential technologies. However, the pace and depth of utilization vary due to infrastructural, financial, and human capacity challenges.

To fully realize the benefits of innovative technologies, universities must adopt a holistic approach that includes strategic planning, sustainable funding, robust ICT infrastructure, and continuous capacity building for both staff and users.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. Increase funding and investment. Federal universities should allocate dedicated funds for the procurement, maintenance, and upgrading of library technologies.
2. Improve ICT infrastructure. Reliable internet connectivity, uninterrupted power supply, and updated computer systems are essential for effective technology adoption.
3. Capacity building and skills development: Libraries should organize regular ICT training and hands-on workshops for library staff and users to enhance their technical competence, digital literacy skills, and confidence in utilizing emerging technologies and digital library services effectively.
4. Awareness and promotion of digital services: Libraries should implement continuous awareness and promotional campaigns through orientations, social media platforms, library websites, and outreach programs to inform users about available digital resources and services and encourage their utilization.
5. Policy support and institutional commitment. University management should integrate library technology goals into institutional ICT policies, ensuring strategic alignment and long-term sustainability.
6. Collaborations and partnerships. Libraries should collaborate with donor agencies, tech companies, and government bodies to source for resources and technical support.

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